

Geopolitics of Continuity: The Arctic Council from Declarations to Statements

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The Arctic Council, established in 1996, has functioned as the most important mechanism for fostering cooperation in the Arctic region, serving as a high-level forum dedicated to promoting environmental protection and sustainable development.¹ The Council comprises Arctic states, non-Arctic states, and Arctic Indigenous Peoples (Permanent Participants), and operates primarily through consensus, utilizing soft law mechanisms via non-binding agreements. As a facilitator rather than a binding decision-making entity, the council has been able to generate significant policy outputs and scientific assessments, thereby influencing Arctic governance.²

The effectiveness of the Arctic Council has been studied extensively.³ However, recent geopolitical changes, most notably the war in Ukraine, have generated further discussions on the end of Arctic exceptionalism⁴ and whether the Arctic Council retains its position as an unshakable bedrock of Arctic cooperation. This article discusses the state of the Arctic Council functionality by examining the council's official documents (i.e., declarations and statements).

Uncertain Times for Arctic Cooperation

Arctic governance has faced significant instability since the Arctic Council suspended operations in March 2022, a situation further complicated by tense relationships among the council's member countries.⁵ Upon assuming the Chairship

¹ Kankaanpää, Paula, and Oran R. Young. "The effectiveness of the Arctic Council." *Polar Research* 31, no. 1 (2012): 171-76.

² Rottem, Svein Vigeland. "The Arctic Council in Arctic Governance." In *The Arctic Council: Between Environmental Protection and Geopolitics*, pp. 47-71. Singapore: Springer Singapore, 2019.

³ Koivurova, Timo. "Limits and possibilities of the Arctic Council in a rapidly changing scene of Arctic governance." *Polar Record* 46, no. 2 (2010): 146-156.

⁴ Devyatkin, Pavel. "Arctic exceptionalism: a narrative of cooperation and conflict from Gorbachev to Medvedev and Putin." *The Polar Journal* 13, no. 2 (2023): 336-357.

⁵ Dyck, Carol, 2024. "Arctic governance in the face of climate change: a case for "inclusive regionalism"", *Canadian Yearbook of International Law/Annuaire Canadien De Droit International*, 61:141-166. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cyl.2024.6>

of the Arctic Council in May 2023, Norway faced considerable uncertainty regarding the operational continuity of the council. In a significant advancement for Arctic multilateral cooperation, all eight Arctic States, in collaboration with the six Indigenous Permanent Participants, achieved a phased resumption of Working Group activities. This process began on August 29, 2023, when a consensus was reached on the modalities for restarting project work using written procedures. Subsequently, in early 2024, further consensus authorized the resumption of official Working Group meetings in a virtual format.⁶ At the same time, political-level engagements remained suspended, and reinstatement of these working-level functions represented an important step forward for the council. As of May 2025, the Kingdom of Denmark holds the Chairship of the Arctic Council for 2025–2027. Chairship is jointly coordinated by Denmark, Greenland, and the Faroe Islands, with Greenland taking a special role.⁷

The Role of Arctic Council Ministerial Meetings

Since its inception, the Arctic Council has convened 14 Ministerial Meetings, beginning with an inaugural session in Iqaluit, Canada, in September 1998 and continuing through the most recent meeting in Tromsø, Norway, in May 2025. These gatherings occur biennially and serve as a formal platform for strategic decision-making among Arctic states and Indigenous Peoples representatives.

Ministerial Meetings serve as the council's highest-level decision-making forum. Their institutional roles include several functions. First, they facilitate the transfer of chairmanship, marking the conclusion of one member state's two-year leadership term and the commencement of another. Second, they provide an opportunity to review progress across the council's six Working Groups.⁸ A defining feature of these meetings was the adoption of a joint declaration. This document articulates the council's priorities and commitments for the forthcoming two-

⁶ Arctic Council, "Arctic Council advances resumption of project-level work," February 28, 2024, <https://arctic-council.org/news/arctic-council-advances-resumption-of-project-level-work/>.

⁷ Arctic Council. "Q&A with Kenneth Høegh, the New Chair of the Senior Arctic Officials." Arctic Council, May 15, 2025. <https://arctic-council.org/news/q-a-with-kenneth-hoegh-new-chair-of-the-senior-arctic-officials>

⁸ Arctic Council, Arctic Council Rules of Procedure (2013), <https://oaarchive.arctic-council.org/items/f06e5457-1246-44d3-a8c1-00016dd585db>.

year term, serving as a normative framework for cooperative action. These declarations incorporated shared objectives in environmental stewardship, sustainable development, and resilience building in the Arctic region.

The formulation of Arctic Council declarations and statements is deeply conditioned by the geopolitical environment in which the council operates. These documents are not just technical outputs; they reflect the prevailing political climate and strategic interests of member states.

Prior to 2022, Ministerial Meetings constituted a diplomatic arena for addressing transboundary issues. Foreign ministers and Permanent Participants engaged in discussions reinforcing the council's role as a consensus-based institution dedicated to safeguarding the Arctic's ecological integrity while promoting equitable development.

From Joint Declarations to Statements

Since its inception, the Arctic Council has issued 11 joint declarations and three statements. To understand their distinct characteristics, the declarations were contrasted with statements. The three statements are the Rovaniemi Joint Ministerial Statement (2019), Arctic Council Statement on the Occasion of the Thirteenth Meeting in Salekhard (2023), and Romssa-Tromsø Statement (2025). The analysis focuses on language, content, and intent from a historical perspective.

The formulation of Arctic Council declarations and statements is deeply conditioned by the geopolitical environment in which the council operates. These documents are not just technical outputs; they reflect the prevailing political climate and strategic interests of member states. Language choices, inclusions, and omissions within such texts often reveal underlying tensions and priorities. The 2019 Rovaniemi Joint Ministerial Statement serves as an example because its drafting process was marked by profound disagreements, as US officials refused to agree to a language that included references to climate change or the Paris

Agreement.⁹ Because the council operates on a consensus basis, this opposition from a single member state made a traditional declaration impossible. As a result, for the first time in its history, the council issued a brief, non-binding statement that omitted contentious climate language, highlighting a significant fracture in the Arctic Council's unity.

The Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022 introduced a profound rupture to Arctic governance. The 2021 Ministerial Meeting was the last high-profile session before the council's operations shifted to a significantly reduced format. Subsequent activities were largely confined to technical work at the Working Group level, signaling a retreat from ministerial diplomacy. This structural adjustment illustrates how external conflicts can constrain multilateral cooperation, even in regions traditionally insulated from global security crises.¹⁰

When analyzing the language of declarations vs. statements, one may see

that declarations use more detailed, prescriptive, and action-oriented language, while statements are brief, concise, and procedural. For instance, the Tromsø Declaration (2009)¹¹ uses directive and action-focused language. It is organized into clear policy sections, such as Climate Change in the Arctic and International Polar Year. The text employs directive and operational language dominated by strong action verbs that convey institutional authority and immediate implementation. The 2019

"... the Rovaniemi Statement had shifted its emphasis toward safeguarding institutional stability, delegating strategic planning, and efficiency reviews to internal mechanisms rather than advancing new policy mandates..."

⁹ Eilís Quinn, "U.S. stonewalling on climate language scuttles Arctic Council declaration," Radio Canada International (Eye on the Arctic), May 7, 2019, <https://www.thebarentsobserver.com/arctic/us-stonewalling-on-climate-language-scuttles-arctic-council-declaration/115763>.

¹⁰ Pedersen, Torbjørn, and Beate Steinveg. "Russia's clashing ambitions: Arctic status quo and world-order revision." *Politics and Governance* 12 (2024).

¹¹ Arctic Council, Tromsø Declaration, Tromsø, Norway, April 29, 2009, <https://oaarchive.arctic-council.org/items/e338fb6f-5096-44b1-9807-76e784ba1c2c>.

Rovaniemi Joint Ministerial Statement, while extremely concise, was high-level and strategic, focusing on reaffirming commitments to peace and stability and issuing broad instructions to Senior Arctic Officials (SAOs) regarding strategic planning and council efficiency.¹² In contrast, the 2023 Salekhard Statement is the briefest and most procedural of all statements. It encompasses seven points that emphasize institutional maintenance and operational continuity, with language dedicated to “*acknowledging the commitment to work to safeguard and strengthen the Arctic Council*” and “*extending the 2022-2023 work plan*”.¹³

The 2009 Tromsø Declaration positioned the council as a global actor, prescribing concrete measures for emission reduction and linking Arctic governance to international climate negotiations, while also addressing maritime safety in response to diminishing sea ice. By 2019, the Rovaniemi Statement had shifted its emphasis toward safeguarding

institutional stability, delegating strategic planning, and efficiency reviews to internal mechanisms rather than advancing new policy mandates. The 2023 Salekhard Statement further narrowed its scope, reducing the content to procedural continuity and operational maintenance, reflecting a period of geopolitical constraints and minimal diplomatic engagement.

The 2025 Tromsø Statement reasserted the council’s relevance. The latest statement confirms that the Arctic Council remains “*the pre-eminent forum for circumpolar cooperation,*” signaling institutional resilience and shared commitment among all Arctic states.¹⁴ The structure of the statement returns to a comprehensive format, organized into thematic sections such as “*People in the North*” and “*Oceans,*” which broadens the scope beyond procedural maintenance. This combination of thematic breadth and directive phrasing confirms that despite geopolitical disruptions, the council is alive, valued, and capable of producing

¹² Arctic Council, Rovaniemi Joint Ministerial Statement, Rovaniemi, Finland, May 7, 2019, <https://oaarchive.arctic-council.org/items/9c932247-27ce-48cd-9eb5-ab1e042fb864>.

¹³ Arctic Council, Arctic Council Statement on the Occasion of the Thirteenth Meeting of the Arctic Council, Salekhard, Russia, May 11, 2023, <https://oaarchive.arctic-council.org/items/5c41807a-27d8-4545-9169-166fc68a7dab>.

¹⁴ Arctic Council, *Romssa - Tromsø Statement*, Romsa - Tromsø, Norway, May 12, 2025, <https://oaarchive.arctic-council.org/items/df62e6fa-0a9f-478c-b0f5-fc8f06a45df4>.

agreements that reinforce continuity and relevance in Arctic governance. This change in communication from declaration to statement demonstrates how external pressures and geopolitical disruptions have reshaped the council's intent from global engagement to pragmatic institutional survival and, more recently, to regionally grounded resilience strategies.

emerging norm for high-level outputs is statements rather than expansive unified declarations.

The question of the Arctic Council's survival, widely debated at the Arctic Circle Assembly 2025, was addressed by Kenneth Høegh, Chair of the Senior Arctic Officials of the Arctic Council, who confirmed that "*The Arctic Council is still alive and very much kicking.*"¹⁵ The 2025 Tromsø Statement signals hope for the future of the council through a return to a comprehensive structure and directive language, demonstrating that despite geopolitical strain, it remains essential for Arctic stability and cooperation. It has been suggested that the Arctic Council should be strengthened through deliberate reform rather than dismissed as obsolete.¹⁶ At the same time, stakeholders may need to acknowledge that the

¹⁵ Trine Jonassen, "Arctic Circle Assembly 2025: 'The Arctic Council is Irreplaceable'," *High North News*, October 19, 2025, <https://www.highnorthnews.com/en/arctic-council-irreplaceable>.

¹⁶ Marisol Maddox and Julia Nesheiwat, "The Arctic Council requires reform, not a funeral: Commentary," *Arctic Today*, October 15, 2025, <https://www.arctictoday.com/the-arctic-council-requires-reform-not-a-funeral/>.